
Testing the Oswald Hypothesis with European Country-Level Data

A Data Management Plan created using dmponline

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Funder: Science Europe

Template: Science Europe

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Project abstract:

The Oswald Hypothesis was first introduced by A.J. Oswald in 1996 where he pointed out a correlation between the homeownership rate and the unemployment rate on a state level. He used simple LS-Regression on the data of the 1960s and 1990s as well as a LS-Regression on the 20-years-changes of these two rates. In all three Regressions, he found a positive correlation of around 0.2. We want to recreate this experiment with European data from the 2000s and 2010s on a national level and see if the Hypothesis holds. We find that the evidence is weak at best before the financial crisis but becomes more sustainable after it.

Last modified: 15-04-2021

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Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

No new data is produced, only existing Data from Eurostat will be re-used.

The data re-used will be filtered and made ready for an easy LS regression on a year-by-year basis that will then be plotted along with the original data.

What data (for example the kinds, formats, and volumes) will be collected or produced?

The project re-uses two external TSV from Eurostat:

1. Dataset: ilc_lvho02, Distribution of population by tenure status, type of household and income group - EU-SILC survey, 1627 KB (accessed on 31 March 2021)
2. Dataset: lfsa_urgan, Unemployment rates by sex, age and citizenship (%), 4476 KB (accessed on 31 March 2021)

These two files can either be found in their most recent form on [the Eurostat website](#) using the search function using the table names (ilc_lvho02 and lfsa_urgan) or in the form used for the experiment in GitHub (<https://github.com/ConBoe/Testing-the-Oswald-Hypothesis-with-European-Country-Level-Data/blob/main/data>). Consistent results of the analysis can only be guaranteed with the data used for the experiment found on GitHub.

Research Output:

1. R version 4.0.3 Code: to clean and filter the data as well as creat graphs. https://github.com/ConBoe/Testing-the-Oswald-Hypothesis-with-European-Country-Level-Data/blob/main/os_hyp_filter_and_analyse.R
2. two CSV files containing the filtered data: unemployment_rate.csv and ownership_rate.csv, size 3KB each. <https://github.com/ConBoe/Testing-the-Oswald-Hypothesis-with-European-Country-Level-Data/blob/main/data>
3. two CSV files: unemployment_rate_flags.csv and ownership_rate_flags.csv, containing the error-flags corresponding to the filtered CSV files (documenting errors from collection), size 3KB each. <https://github.com/ConBoe/Testing-the-Oswald-Hypothesis-with-European-Country-Level-Data/blob/main/data>

Documentation and data quality

What metadata and documentation (for example the methodology of data collection and way of organising data) will accompany data?

The data will be accompanied by

- a README.md file with an explanation of the experiment as well instructions on how to recreate it
- zip files with SDMX Metadata Structure (ESMS) from Eurostat for the downloaded data
- txt files with dates of the latest content and structural updates of the downloaded data tables
- table codes from Eurostat to identify the used tables in their internal system
- code lists from the Eurostat that are relevant for the analysis (e.g. tenure types and country codes)
- links to the Eurostat official metadata concerning the relevant tables
- a link to the Github repository where the downloaded, as well as the filtered tables, will be available in TSV and CSV form respectively

What data quality control measures will be used?

The data from Eurostat is subject to ESS-Validation.

Storage and backup during the research process

How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research process?

During the project data and metadata will be stored on a local PC as well as on a GitHub repository.

<https://github.com/ConBoe/Testing-the-Oswald-Hypothesis-with-European-Country-Level-Data>

How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

The project produces nor uses any sensitive data.

Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on data security be ensured?

No personal data is processed.

How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

Re-used Data:

The data re-used from [Eurostat](#) is under a CC-BY 4.0 license as stated on the Website of the [European Commission](#).

The owner of the code and produced Data is Constantin Boerner.

The code will be licensed under the MIT license.

The data produced will be under a CC-BY 4.0 license.

How will possible ethical issues be taken into account, and codes of conduct followed?

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project.

Data sharing and long-term preservation

How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

Data will be shared on Zenodo as well as GitHub at the finalization of the project.

At the moment, we are not aware of any restrictions on the re-use of data. If issues arise during the project, we will update the information in the DMP.

How will data for preservation be selected, and where will data be preserved long-term (for example a data repository or archive)?

Data prepared for the analysis will be preserved long-term. Intermediate results will not be saved.

For long-term archiving of and access to the datasets, the Zenodo repository will be used. For source code, GitHub will be used, where also Zenodo can be used for archiving and creating a persistent identifier.

DOI Badge of the Data:

10.5281/zenodo.4679520 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4679520>

DOI Badge of the Graphics: 10.5281/zenodo.4679641

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4679641> DOI Badge of Github repositories:

What methods or software tools will be needed to access and use the data?

The data will be stored in CSV files to make them as accessible as possible.

The code will be written using R Version.

For access to the metadata software for zip like WinRAR is needed. Furthermore, software to work with SDMX 2.1 is needed as well.

How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier (such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI)) to each data set be ensured?

The persistent identifier will be assigned by the repositories.

Data management responsibilities and resources

Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management (i.e. the data steward)?

As a sole contributor, Constantin Boerner will take responsibility for the data management.

What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

No financial resources are required for the project as all tools and sources used are free of charge.

Time will be dedicated by Constantin Boerner as necessary and available corresponding with his other obligations (e.g. other lectures).

